

The Collatz primes conjecture

Adolf Cusmariu

Email: adolcus@gmail.com

Let $C_3(t)$ be the Collatz function

$$C_3(t) = (3t + 1)/2 \quad \text{for } t \text{ odd}$$

Call a prime p a 'Collatz prime' if $C_3(p)$ is also prime.

Let

$$\pi(x) = \#\{\text{primes } p: 2 < p \leq x\}$$

be the usual prime counter starting at 3, and

$$\sigma(x) = \#\{\text{Collatz primes } p: 2 < p \leq x\}$$

The Collatz Primes Conjecture:

$$\sigma(x) \rightarrow \pi(x)/2\log_{10}(\pi(x)) \quad \text{for sufficiently large } x$$

Reference

A. Cusmariu, 'Collatz on more primes', <https://zenodo.org/records/10871130>, 2024